

BOSHLANG'ICH SINFLARDA MATEMATIKA O'QITISH METODIKASIDA INTERFAOL METODLARDAN FOYDALANISH

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Annotation: Socio-economic relations in the country, changes in the public education system, as reflected in the Law "On Education" and the "National Training Program" an important task is set before the primary school teacher. These tasks allow to distinguish the specific links for primary education, which are connected with the introduction of education in different curricula, curricula, textbooks, as well as a network in the methodological system. can form. When we say the methodological-mathematical training of a primary school teacher, we mean the preparation of the methodology of teaching mathematics on the basis of a scientific worldview in an integral connection with the general pedagogical-psychological and mathematical training. The task of such preparation is to acquire certain knowledge and skills in mathematics in the field of primary education, as well as to master the upbringing of children through teaching.

Keywords: Mathematics, arithmetic, method, cluster, methodology, addition, equation, subtraction, calculation, comparison.

USE OF INTERACTIVE METHODS IN THE TEACHING OF MATHEMATICS IN PRIMARY SCHOOL.

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Abstract: Socio-economic relations in our country, changes in the system of public education, as reflected in the Law "On Education" and the "National Program of Personnel Training" an important task is set before the inner class teacher. These tasks allow to distinguish the specific links for primary education, which are connected with the introduction of education in different curricula, curricula, textbooks, as well as a network in the methodological system. can form. When we say the methodological-mathematical training of a primary school teacher, we mean the preparation of the methodology of teaching mathematics on the basis of a scientific worldview in an integral connection with the general pedagogical-psychological and mathematical training. The task of such preparation is to acquire certain knowledge and skills in mathematics in the field of primary education, as well as to master the upbringing of children through teaching.

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An elementary math course helps children develop thinking. At the same time it creates a unique set of basic knowledge, on the other hand, will be focused on the formation of the necessary methodological assumptions and logical structures of thinking. Psychologists have proven that it is a period responsible for the formation of thinking skills of children aged 6-10 years. Therefore, one of the tasks of the methodology of primary education, in particular, the methodology of primary education in mathematics, is to accelerate the impact of teaching on the mental development of children while ensuring a sufficiently high developmental efficiency of teaching. Can solve basic educational tasks in mathematics only on the basis of a system of theoretical knowledge. This includes the scientific worldview, psychology, didactics, the theory of teaching mathematics (mathematical didactics). However, theoretical knowledge alone is not enough. Ability to apply the most effective methods for this or that area of study, which is affected by the specific content of teaching and the level of mental activity of the teacher. necessary. It is important for the primary school teacher to know and take into account the level and capabilities of the students' mental activities as it lays the foundation for the mental development of the children in the primary grades. Various methodological issues arising in the process of practical application of theoretical knowledge should be addressed. Methodological issues arise in every lesson, however, they usually do not have a single valuable solution. The teacher needs to be sufficiently prepared in this area in order to be able to quickly find the most appropriate solution to the methodological problem that arises in the lesson for this learning situation. Didactic games are used as a teaching tool in primary education due to the lack of content in terms of logic and mathematics, and didactic games are used only as a means of reinforcing the material studied. 5 Problems arise in the content of teaching a child from 6-7 years. This is solved by teaching in kindergartens. Learning to count, addition and multiplication in the first stage (within 20) has been a major task of primary education. However, this task is not unique, but it is a broader and more comprehensive part of the preparatory work for the study of children's mathematics is determined in two main ways: 1) the pedagogical way, ie the mathematical way in which children's thinking is applied preparation for feedback; 2) to prepare the child for the study of the most important

mathematical concepts and, first of all, the concepts of natural numbers and geometric shapes.

The word mathematics is derived from the Greek word “mathema,” which means “to know science”.⁶ The object of study of the science of mathematics consists of spatial forms and the quantitative relations between them. The purpose of a school mathematics course is to provide students with a system of mathematical knowledge that takes into account their psychological characteristics. This system of mathematical knowledge is conveyed to students through certain methods. “Methodology” is a Greek word, and “method” means “yoI”. Mathematical methodology is a branch of pedagogical science, which is part of the system of pedagogical sciences, and in accordance with the goals of teaching set by society, implements the laws of teaching mathematics at a certain stage of mathematical development. The setting of new goals in teaching has led to a radical change in the content of teaching mathematics. In order for primary school students to be effectively taught mathematics, the teacher must master and master the methodology of teaching mathematics in primary school. The subject of the methodology of primary education in mathematics is:

1. Substantiation of the purpose of teaching mathematics (why mathematics is taught, taught).

2. The development of the content of teaching mathematics (what to teach), how to distribute the level of knowledge in a system in accordance with the age characteristics of students, to ensure consistency in the study of the basics of science, The burden of education is eliminated, the content of education corresponds to the ability of your student to acquire specific knowledge.

3. Scientific development of teaching methods (how to teach, that is, what are the methods of teaching so that students acquire the economic knowledge, skills, abilities and intellectual abilities needed today?

4. The use of teaching aids - textbooks, didactic materials, visual aids and teaching aids (how to teach).

5. Preliminary development of the organization of education (how to organize the lesson and extracurricular forms of education):

The methodology of teaching mathematics, first of all, sets the task of teaching and educating young students in the general system. The general methodology reflects the content and structure of elementary school mathematics, teaching each section its own specific methods of teaching. The specific methodology shows the basic methods and forms of teaching

mathematics, as well as 10 ways to organize learning activities. It is well known that teaching is inextricably linked with upbringing. This methodology teaches ways to combine teaching with parenting. The methodology of teaching mathematics in the primary grades is closely related to several disciplines: 1) with mathematics, which is the basis of teaching; 2) pedagogy; 3) psychology; 4) with other teaching methods (native language, labor). In primary school, a mathematics course has become a subject. The teaching objectives of the methodology of teaching mathematics in primary school are: a) the implementation of educational and practical tasks; b) cover the process of studying the system of theoretical knowledge; d) teach your student how to shape their worldview; e) humanization of education; . f) in the process of teaching mathematics to show a person to love work, to cultivate such qualities as self-respect, mutual respect; g) teaching methodology consists of teaching in connection with the content of mathematics of V-VI grades, which is a continuation of mathematics of I-IV grades. The task of the elementary mathematics course is to help the school to solve the task of "using new technologies to teach students the basics of science, to provide them with modern socio-economic knowledge, interest in the profession, to teach them to make informed choices." consists of giving. Thus, like any other subject, the purpose of teaching an elementary course in mathematics is determined by the following three factors:

1. The general educational purpose of teaching mathematics;
2. Educational purpose of teaching mathematics;
3. The practical purpose of teaching mathematics. The general educational purpose of teaching mathematics is the following task. Methods of teaching mathematics in preparatory groups The preparatory group of kindergarten is planned to conduct two lessons a week, 72-74 lessons a year. Classes are held from September to the end of May, each lasting 25-30 minutes. Didactic games and visual aids are widely used in the lessons. In order for children to be interested in the lessons, the educator must meet the following requirements:
 1. Good mastery of the program materials.
 2. Prepare thorough material (demonstration and distribution).
 3. Focus on changing children's activities and the interests of the link. .
 4. Schedule action games between sessions.
 5. Get your child to draw independent conclusions during the lesson.

6. Encourage your child to respond differently. When distributing the program material to the lessons, it is necessary to pay attention to the knowledge and skills of the child, the readiness of the child. It is important to be able to use specific terms correctly. For example, it is important not to confuse the concepts of numbers and figures. "Which number is bigger and which is smaller" (which number is not big) is asked. At the same time, all children try to listen carefully to the answers of their peers, discipline is not violated, so the child's preparation for tests should be taken into account. Introduction to numbers from 9 to 9 . Children are not taught to write numbers, they are only introduced to the printed form. Children should be able to distinguish which number is the sign of each number. There are 10 numbers in each case: 0,1,2,3,4,5,6 , 7,8,9. There is no number 10. The number 10 is denoted by two numbers: 1 and 0. In one lesson, one or two numbers can be introduced. For example, when introducing the number "1", t the soldier puts one toy on the counting card, puts 1 circle card in front of the link. Calling 2 kids, one offers to jump once, the other to knock on the table once. The children count and conclude that each is one. Then pointing to the number "1" is a conditional sign indicating that the number means that each number has its own sign.

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